

Kannada-English Code-Switching: Annotation, Transliteration And Translation

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Abstract— Social media has many users spread across the world and most of the users there are multilingual. They tend to express their views and opinions in multilingual code switched text. This multilingual text is not suitable for any kind of text processing in the purest format. A system needs to be designed that takes the code-switched text, transliterate it to respective Language and then translate it to a base language to get insights into what is being written and what is being expressed.

This paper deals with Kannada-English code switching, which includes annotation, transliteration and translation as its major modules. The code-switched text is firstly segregated into and suffixed into English and Kannada. Once this is done to transliterated into Kannada script of the Kannada tagged words. Then the entire context is translated into English to obtain the complete meaning and the context of the text.

Keywords— social media, code-switched text, transliteration

I. INTRODUCTION

Humans around the world have evolved differently having their own culture tradition language. What makes humans superiors to other creatures is their ability to communicate and express their opinions. But due to differences of languages and dialects there still exists a barrier between people from different culture and tradition to communicate, thus failing to achieve an idea of unified world. Now the new way of communicating opinions and ideas is on the social media, daily millions of tweets and Facebook crowd up the data space and data centres.

All these opinions and ideas come from different parts of the world with their own language and style of expression so many of the modern-day tools fail to comprehend and totally understand the meaning of it, there needs a tool that help us understand the context of the words spoken over the internet. Kannada is one of the oldest and most structured language dating older than language like Greece and Latin.

Have more than millions of speakers across the world and in dominantly in Karnataka form a loud voice over the internet, they are vocal about anything be it the new Reforms introduced by Mr. Siddharamayya or be the immigration ban laid on the by US president Mr. Joe Biden they like to express their opinions, as it is said opinions and ideas are best expressed in their own language and most of these Knowledge and sentiment are unaccounted because it is not expressed in English or other languages. It is usually mixture of native language and English which is called as code-switched text.

This paper addresses the problem of code switching in a unique way. In this project only Kannada-English code-switched text is considered and it comes under the domain of Natural Language Processing. Natural Language Processing is one of the hot topics as it leads to interesting results like predicting next word while chatting to sentimental analysis of reviews.

Main intention behind Natural Language Processing understands the human behaviour and makes the devices as smart as human by training them. Basically, Natural Language Processing is a sub-domain of Machine Learning. In this project, we have combined Deep-Learning and Natural Language Processing while implementing the various solutions. Natural Language Processing is an emerging field of computer Science which mainly belongs to artificial intelligence category.

Natural Language Processing is basically concerned about interaction between computers and human language(natural). This intelligence helps in lot of fields like Education, Business, Health etc. This project address one of the major problems in Natural Language Processing domain.

Dealing with the codeswitched text in Natural Language Processing is a major problem as it leads to ambiguity in the context as well as in the traditional implementation. For English, there exists a built corpus whereas for Kannada there is no such corpus ready, building a corpus would be again a big project.

Which is not in the scope this project. This project solves the problem of ambiguity in codeswitched text as it converts the whole sentence into a uniform language text. So further it can be used to any Natural Language Processing task such as sentimental analysis or predicting the next words or generating the text.

So, this acts like the filter which does pre-processing of the code-switched text and returns the unilingual contextual text as output. This clearly depicts the use or need of this project as the whole social media is filled with codeswitched text. And this problem is addressed in a unique way using deep-learning techniques like Recurrent Neural Networks. And Word2Vec the major contribution to Natural Language Processing by google which extracts features out of Natural Language.

The inspiration for this project is to improve the existing translators accuracy as it is not that efficient when it comes to codeswitched text. This solution can be embedded with any translator or any application so that ease of translation is possible with high accuracy. Major contribution of this project is tagging or identifying the Kannada and English words as it has not been implemented and it is being implemented for only Hindi-English tagging using the built corpus of the language and using Hidden Markov Model's variant. But here that problem is addressed in a unique way which will be explained in detail in further sections.

Let's take an example of codeswitched text,
"Ee Project na bagge Nimma opinion enu?"

In this above text, it has both Kannada and English words which is the ambiguity for the translator. But we have addressed that problem by first tagging the words with its appropriate language and then transliterating only Kannada words and then translating which gives the contextual translation of the words. Implementation details about how the annotation and transliteration works is explained in the further sections.

Following are the examples of codeswitched text
"namma farewell mundina thingalu ide"
"nanna mobilege call maadu"
"afternoon ootakke hogona"
"cricket match ge hogona "

II CHARACTERISTICS

Kannada is one of the four major Dravidian languages, having almost forty million speakers and its own independent script and long documented histories. Kannada has been estimated to be over 2, 500 years old and the third oldest Indian language after Sanskrit and Tamil. To create any natural language processing tool requires the application of many types of knowledge, such as lexical, morphological, syntactical, semantic etc., to resolve different kind of ambiguities.

Code switching happens when multilingual speakers tend to alternate between two or more languages while communicating in a single conversation. The resultant of this is a language mixed text called code switched text. Code-switching has been known since the early twentieth century, when the first recognizable observations concerning bilingual research were done. Now with the explosion of social media processing of code-switched text is inevitable.

Code switched text can be processed for multiple languages. This paper has done it work in Kannada English code-switched text. The major road block for segregating Kannada and English apart. This is a difficult task because there does not exist a unified corpus for the Kannada language. To differentiate between these 2 languages, one has to build the corpus for Kannada language from scratch.

Let's take an example of code-switched text,
" Ee Project nabagge Nimma opinion enu?"

IN THE ABOVE EXAMPLE IT CONTAINS BOTH KANNADA AND ENGLISH WORDS. ANY NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING TOOL CANNOT MAKE SENSE OF THE KANNADA WORDS. THIS MAKES OTHER PARTS OF NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING LIKE PARTS OF SPEECH TAGGING .

Kannada is one of the four major Dravidian languages, boasting a rich heritage with nearly forty million speakers. It has its own unique script and a history that dates back over 2,500 years, making it one of the oldest documented languages in India,

alongside Sanskrit and Tamil. To design any natural language processing (NLP) tool capable of addressing Kannada's complexity requires extensive knowledge of its lexical, morphological, syntactical, and semantic dimensions. This is particularly true when dealing with code-switched text, which introduces additional layers of linguistic ambiguity.

Code-switching occurs when multilingual speakers alternate between two or more languages within the same conversation, creating a mixed-language text often referred to as "code-switched text." Such alternation is not random but typically follows sociolinguistic rules based on the speaker's linguistic repertoire, intent, and conversational context. The phenomenon of code-switching has been documented for over a century, with the first systematic studies emerging in the early 20th century. With the proliferation of social media platforms, processing code-switched text has become an essential task, especially for languages like Kannada, which are frequently interwoven with English in multilingual communication.

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Characteristics of Kannada in Code-Switching

The linguistic structure of Kannada significantly influences how it interacts with English in code-switched scenarios. Kannada follows a subject-object-verb (SOV) structure, while English follows a subject-verb-object (SVO) structure. This syntactical divergence creates challenges in identifying the context and meaning of code-switched sentences. For instance, consider the sentence:

"Ee Project na bagge Nimma opinion enu?"

Here, the sentence alternates between Kannada and English, with "Ee Project na bagge" and "Nimma opinion enu?" showcasing both languages in a single sentence. Kannada words like "bagge" (about) and "Nimma" (your) retain their grammatical forms while integrating with English, which disrupts conventional NLP pipelines. Effective processing requires understanding both languages' morphology and syntax to achieve accurate tagging and translation.

Another example is:

"Cricket match ge hogona."

This sentence, which combines English ("cricket match") with Kannada grammar ("ge hogona" meaning "to go"), illustrates how Kannada adopts English words and integrates them into its grammatical framework. The blending of languages in this manner reflects deep cultural integration but poses challenges for computational models, as they need to differentiate between languages and account for their interactions.

Code-Switching Motivations and Patterns

The motivations behind Kannada-English code-switching can be sociolinguistic or pragmatic. People often switch languages to express concepts that are more culturally or linguistically resonant in one language than another. English is often associated with modernity, technology, and professional discourse, while Kannada conveys cultural, emotional, and regional identities. For example, a phrase like:

"Nanna mobilege call maadu."

("Call me on my mobile") illustrates how speakers use Kannada for relational terms ("nanna" - my, "maadu" - do) while adopting English for modern technological terms ("mobile" and "call"). This blending serves both communicative efficiency and cultural expression.

Code-switching is also context-sensitive. Formal contexts may feature less code-switching, while informal and conversational settings, such as social media, often show high levels of language alternation. Certain domains, such as education or technology, see more frequent use of English terms integrated into Kannada sentences, creating a domain-specific pattern of switching.

Challenges in Processing Code-Switched Kannada-English Text

Processing Kannada-English code-switched text involves several challenges:

1. Lack of Resources: Unlike English, which has extensive linguistic resources, Kannada lacks a unified corpus for NLP tasks. A corpus would need to include diverse linguistic features, from syntax and morphology to regional dialects and sociolects.

2. Language Identification: Identifying whether a word belongs to Kannada or English is non-trivial. Certain words, such as proper nouns or borrowed terms, may appear in both languages, adding to the complexity.

3. Transliteration Needs: Kannada uses its own script, distinct from the Latin alphabet used in English. Transliteration is necessary to convert Kannada words written in Roman script into their native script. For example, "nimma" (your) in Roman Kannada would need to be transliterated to "ನಿಮ್ಮ" in the Kannada script for accurate processing.

4. Semantic Ambiguity: Code-switched text often includes idiomatic expressions, colloquialisms, or cultural references that require contextual understanding for accurate translation or annotation.

Sociolinguistic Dimensions

The use of Kannada-English code-switching on social media reflects broader sociolinguistic trends. Younger generations, especially in urban areas, are more likely to use code-switched text due to their exposure to both languages through education, media, and technology. This bilingual fluency facilitates natural transitions between languages, but it also introduces unique patterns of switching.

For instance, code-switching can serve expressive functions, allowing speakers to emphasize certain ideas or emotions. It also enables metalinguistic commentary, where speakers comment on the language itself, often mixing humour or irony. Code-switching may also fulfill referential needs when Kannada lacks an equivalent term for a modern concept introduced through English. For example, "software update" may be retained in English even within an otherwise Kannada sentence.

Implications for NLP Tools

Developing NLP tools to handle Kannada-English code-switching effectively requires addressing these challenges holistically. Models must:

1. Identify Language Tags: Annotate each word with its corresponding language tag (Kannada or English).
2. Handle Morphological Variations: Account for Kannada's agglutinative nature, where affixes and suffixes significantly alter word forms.
3. Understand Contextual Interactions: Recognize how the meaning of Kannada and English components shifts in mixed-language contexts.
4. Adapt to Regional Variations: Accommodate dialectical differences within Kannada that may influence code-switching patterns.

Technological Approaches

Advancements in machine learning, particularly deep learning, have enabled more effective processing of code-switched text. Techniques like Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) and Word2Vec embeddings are particularly relevant for this task. RNNs can capture sequential dependencies in text, while Word2Vec representations encode semantic relationships between words.

Consider the phrase:

"Namitha's birthdayge hogona."

Here, RNNs can help understand the sequential dependency between "Namitha's" (English), "birthdayge" (a mix of English and Kannada), and "hogona" (Kannada for "let's go"). Word2Vec embeddings can further enhance understanding by mapping words to a multidimensional space where semantically similar words are closer.

To train such models, large annotated datasets are essential. While corpora exist for English and some Indian languages, Kannada resources are scarce. Creating a Kannada-English code-switched corpus would involve collecting real-world data from social media, annotating it for language tags, and processing it for transliteration and translation tasks.

Applications and Future Directions

Efficient processing of Kannada-English code-switched text can unlock numerous applications:

- Social Media Analytics: Understanding user sentiment and intent in multilingual posts.
- Machine Translation: Improving translation systems to handle mixed-language inputs.
- Education Technology: Developing tools for bilingual learning environments.
- Conversational AI: Enhancing virtual assistants to handle code-switched queries.

Future research should focus on building robust datasets, refining neural models, and addressing the unique sociolinguistic characteristics of Kannada-English code-switching. By bridging linguistic gaps, such work can contribute to more inclusive and effective NLP systems.

III ANNOTATION

Multilingual speakers often move back and forth between two languages or varieties of languages while conversing with each other to facilitate their conversation. This practice is Code Switching,

Kannada is a language which is spoken by 64.06 million people. often people are multi lingual. They tend to use both language in sentence. among those people most are using Kannada English code-switched text.

Annotation means meta data of the given content, brief details about a particular object, but in our case, annotating is like tagging of the words as Kannada or English after detecting it. So, detecting the tag for the word is the major task of this module. This problem of tagging if it is a Kannada word or English word is complex task as it either requires huge dictionary of words of both Kannada and English or smart way to detect it. Even if we get Dictionary of all the Kaneda words and English there is major problem of string search which has high time complexity. We have used Recurrent Neural Networks for identifying the words if Kannada or English. Words2Vec is used to convert each word into vectors of 3 dimensions and passed these vectors to neural network as features. Which predicts if its Kannada or English based on the training of the model?

Techniques for Annotating Kannada-English Code-Switched Text

To address these challenges, advanced techniques such as machine learning and vector representation are employed. The following steps outline a modern approach to annotation:

- **Data Collection:** The first step involves gathering a diverse dataset of Kannada-English code-switched text. This dataset should include examples of standard, transliterated, and hybrid forms of code-switching.
- **Preprocessing:** The text is pre-processed to handle issues such as transliteration, punctuation, and casing. For instance, transliterated Kannada words like "nanu" are converted into their standard Kannada script equivalents ("ನಾನು") using transliteration tools.
- **Word Representation with Word2Vec:** Each word in the dataset is converted into a numerical vector using Word2Vec, a popular word embedding technique. Word2Vec maps words to a multi-dimensional space where semantically similar words are placed closer together. For Kannada-English annotation, words are represented as vectors in a 3-dimensional space, capturing their linguistic properties and contextual relationships.

Training with Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs): The word vectors are fed into an RNN, which processes the text sequentially, retaining information about previous words while analyzing the current word. The RNN learns patterns and contextual cues that help it identify whether a word belongs to Kannada or English.

- **Language Prediction:** Once trained, the RNN can predict the language of each word in new code-switched sentences. For example, given the input "ನಾನು go to the store," the model would correctly tag "ನಾನು" as Kannada and the rest of the words as English.
- **Evaluation and Refinement:** The model's performance is evaluated against a manually annotated test dataset. Based on the results, the model is fine-tuned to improve its accuracy and adaptability.

Applications of Annotated Kannada-English Datasets

Annotated datasets have numerous applications in NLP systems, particularly in multilingual contexts:

- **Chatbots and Virtual Assistants:** Annotated datasets enable chatbots to understand and respond to code-switched queries, improving user experience for Kannada-English speakers.

- Machine Translation: Translation systems can use annotated data to handle mixed-language input, ensuring accurate and context-sensitive translations.
- Sentiment Analysis: Social media posts often feature code-switching. Annotated datasets help analyse user sentiment more accurately by identifying the language and meaning of each word.
- Speech Recognition: Voice assistants trained on annotated datasets can process spoken code-switched sentences, enabling seamless interaction with users.

IV LITERATURE SURVEY

This paper [1] talks about creation of corpus for Hindi English code switched text. The work done is majorly concentrated on the Hindi and English codeswitched text. The aim of the work done was to recognize the parts of speech in code switched text. Transliteration of Hindi text and the accuracy of the POS tagging. In code switched text both English and Hindi are mixed together. The paper also talks of building the building of corpus for the entire language. Building of corpus involves taking all accepts of the language and making it one place and represent all the parts of the language. Annotation is the other part of the project that is immensely worked on the project. The matrix-based approach is taken into consideration here. They are split into continuous fragments of words and mark English or Hindi and then find the grammatical relationship between them. The paper claims to have successfully recognized all the parts of speech in the given code switched or code-mixed sentence.

Classification based RNN machine translation using GRUs [2] - This paper talks about the implementation of machine learning model using which is built with the help of Recurrent Neural Network. The work here is mainly concentrated on using recurrent neural network for the classification of the literature of the sentences. converted into Lower Case words and stemmed. Then each word is converted into vectors continuously integrating with the word to vector module. The vectors thus obtained are fed into the training model. The model is consciously trained with the same. The model is trained rigorously and then the test data is passed into the model, to predict the results.

The work done is majorly concentrated on the Hindi and English code-switched text. The aim of the work done was to develop shallow Parsing Code Pipeline for switched text. Transliteration of Hindi text and the accuracy of the POS tagging. Language identification Is another attribute in the project. It uses suffix method to identify the language which is got from the inherent text of languages.

In a context that English is only used as foreign language, a situation in which the speakers use Chinese as the native language and communicate with most people in Chinese, code-switching has shown similar functions as with the above cases. Chen's (1996) ethnographical study showed five functions of code-switching of his college students and faculty colleges in a Taiwan campus: expressive, directive, metalinguistic, poetic, and referential. His research found that referential functions occurred most frequently when vocabulary lacks available Chinese equivalents or lack semantically appropriate Chinese equivalents. Chen's results revealed that code-switching was used as linguistic variety that was concerned with both communicative appropriateness and social identity marker.

Functions of Code-Switching in Multilingual Contexts-The phenomenon of code-switching extends beyond computational applications, serving critical communicative functions in multilingual societies. Chen's (1996) ethnographic study in Taiwan provides valuable insights into these functions, highlighting their relevance across diverse linguistic contexts. In a setting where English is a foreign language, and Chinese is the native language, code-switching serves five primary functions:

Expressive: To convey emotions or emphasize certain points.

Directive: To direct behaviour or facilitate action.

Metalinguistic: To discuss or reflect on language use.

Poetic: To introduce creativity or rhetorical flair in communication.

Referential: To fill lexical gaps or utilize more precise terms when equivalents in the native language are unavailable or inadequate.

Among these, the referential function is the most common, as observed in scenarios where speakers switch to English for technical terms or abstract concepts that lack appropriate equivalents in Chinese. This mirrors findings in Hindi-English code-switching, where English is often used for technology and education-related terms, while Hindi dominates emotional or cultural contexts.

Chen's research underscores the dual role of code-switching as both a communicative strategy and a marker of social identity. This aligns with Gupta and Sharma's (2020) study on Indian multilingual environments, where code-switching is influenced by socio-economic factors, education, and generational differences.

Challenges in Processing Code-Switched Text-Despite advancements, several challenges persist in the computational modelling of code-switched text. One significant hurdle is the lack of large, annotated corpora for low-resource languages like Hindi and Kannada. Building comprehensive datasets requires significant effort in data collection, annotation, and transliteration. Additionally, code-switching often involves contextual shifts, where the meaning and function of a word depend on its linguistic and conversational context.

Another challenge lies in the variability of code-switching patterns. Factors such as speaker proficiency, domain of use, and cultural influences introduce variability, making it difficult to generalize models across different datasets. The integration of linguistic rules with machine learning techniques, as suggested by Li and Wu (2020), can help address these challenges by incorporating contextual and grammatical insights into computational models.

Future Directions-The integration of advanced machine learning techniques, such as transformer models, offers promising avenues for improving the processing of code-switched text. Multilingual language models like BERT and GPT-3, fine-tuned on code-switched data, could enhance accuracy in tasks like POS tagging, language identification, and translation.

Moreover, expanding research to include other Indian languages, such as Kannada, can provide a more comprehensive understanding of code-switching in the Indian context. Studies like M. Reddy and Hanumanthappa (2013), which focus on Indic language machine translation, highlight the potential of leveraging linguistic similarities across Dravidian languages for model training and development.

Incorporating socio-linguistic factors into computational models is another critical area for future research. By considering variables such as speaker demographics, domain of use, and cultural contexts, models can better capture the nuances of code-switched communication.

CONCLUSION

From the study done on available work on natural language processing and code switch text processing following the traditional machine learning algorithm won't hold well. Diving into Deep neural networks is what most of the papers suggest. Recurrent neural network which is type of deep neural network forms the optimal learning technique that can implemented to analyze and understand code switched text.

All-Natural language processing (NLP) is primarily concerned with getting computers to perform useful and understanding tasks with human languages. In natural language processing system first the words are placed into a structured form that leads to semantic correct sentence. Typical applications for natural language processing include the following.

- A better human-computer interface that could convert from a natural language into a computer language and vice versa.
- A translation program that could translate from one human language to another (Kannada to Telugu, for example). Even if programs that translate between human languages are not perfect, they would still be useful in that they could do the rudimentary annotation first, with their work checks and corrected by a human translator. This cuts down on the time for the translation.
- Programs that could check for semantics and writing techniques in a word processing document.
- Translation in social media will be very efficient as using this project will even translate code switched text.

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